

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION OF HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY
IN THE STORIES OF A.P. CHEKHOV.

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Abstract: This article presents a scientific and theoretical analysis of the issue of artistic aesthetic depiction of human psychology in the stories of Anton Pavlovich Chekhov.

Keywords: Ordinary people, inherent virtue, position, light, variability, human nature, social conditions, problem, simplicity, deep image, originality, etc.

Introduction: Anton Pavlovich Chekhov is a great writer who reflected simple but profound social and psychological aspects of life in his short stories. His story "Chameleon" is one of the works that reveals important aspects of human psychology. Through this story, Chekhov deeply explores such features of humanity as variability, greed, and hypocrisy.

Literature analysis: One of the main features of Chekhov's stories is the harmony of realism and psychologism. He is a master of simple but profound depictions of life, and the events in the stories are taken from ordinary human life. Chekhov's characters are distinguished by their vitality: they are ordinary people, with their own qualities and shortcomings. For example, in the story "Chameleon" the usual aspects of life - careerism and hypocrisy - are depicted in a satirical tone. Through this story, Chekhov raises universal problems in Russian society, such as the domination of the strong over the weak.

The title of the story prepares the reader for one of the most basic psychological aspects of humanity - the concept of change depending on the situation. A chameleon is a creature that changes its color to adapt to temperature, light, or other external conditions. Chekhov uses this metaphor to describe people who change their positions depending on different life situations.

The main character of the story, police inspector Ochumelov, seeks his own interests in every situation. At first glance, he seems strict and fair, but as soon as circumstances change, he reconsiders his decision. This situation reveals an interesting psychological mechanism in human nature: people are inclined to favor the strong and seek to protect only their own interests. Ochumelov changes his mind several times while trying to determine who the dog belongs to. This shows that he has no personal principles.

The power of public opinion is also clearly manifested in Chekhov's story. Ochumelov's decisions are guided by the attitude of the people around him. People who change their position depending on the opinions of others are not only heroes in the story, but also in real life. This indicates a person's tendency to succumb to external influences rather than to independently realize himself.

Social pressure in society, people's respect or fear of higher officials are psychologically reflected in Ochumelov's actions. If the dog belongs to a rich person, he is ready to forgive a minor offense; on the contrary, if the dog belongs to an ordinary person, he immediately seeks to toughen the punishment. This reveals the contradiction in how people behave in front of powerful figures in society.

Another important aspect of the story "Hamilion" is hypocrisy. It is manifested not only in the character of Ochumelov, but also in other characters in the story. This feature of human nature is an important theme for Chekhov, who shows it vividly and interestingly through life events. Ochumelov always tries to show his strengths, but his actions are hypocritical.

The root of hypocrisy lies in a person's desire for inner security. The source of such actions is usually various social pressures in society or expected results. This aspect encourages readers to think deeply and discover the complexities of human behavior.

Chekhov's story "Hamilion" encourages the reader to think about human relationships in society. Through this work, the writer tells us that the basic problems of human nature, such as hypocrisy and self-interest, are the root of many problems in society. That is why this work of Chekhov is relevant for modern society.

Chekhov has a unique style of revealing the drama in the lives of ordinary people. There are almost no extraordinary events in his stories; but through the small details of everyday life, it reveals a whole world of human experiences. "The Man from the Village" depicts the struggle between human dreams and the disappointments of real life. This story shows the contrast between city and village life, as well as the injustices of life and human weakness.

Conclusion: A.P. Chekhov's story "Hamilion" is an invaluable work that reveals the complex and multifaceted nature of human psychology. Every detail in the story, the actions and dialogues of the characters, vividly and clearly depict the main problems of human behavior. Chekhov's skill lies in the fact that he is able to depict complex social and psychological problems through a simple story. For

this reason, "Hamilion" is considered not only as a literary work, but also as an important source for studying human nature.

References:

- 1.K.F.Muminovna. GENESIS OF THE ORIGINS OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE'S VIEWS ON FIRE. Chiet Editor.
- 2.F.Karimova. PEOPLE'S VITAL NEED FOR FIRE.International Conference on Business Management and Humanities 1(1).130-133.
- 3.K K Akhmadovich, O B Togmurodovich NEW STAGES AND PRACTICAL CONDITIONS FOR CREATING NATIONAL TEXTBOOKS AND ALPHABET BOOKS.Conferencea, 54-58.
- 4.K K Akhmadovich, SG Badriddinnovna THE CONCERT OF READING, SPECIAL FEATURES OF CHILDREN'S READING E Conferencea,28-33.
- 5.KK Akhmadovich, N O Alisherovna THE AESTHETIC VALUE OF LINGUISTIC FLORIONYMS IN WORKS OF ART IN AROUSING LAUGHTER 59-63.
- 6..K K Akhmadovich, O B Togmurodovich THE ISSUE OF THE CONTENT OF EDUCATION IN THE HISTORY OF THE PEOPLES OF THE EAST Conferencea, 95-101.
- 7.K K Akhmadovich, S G Badriddinovna HISTORICAL GENESIS OF UZBEK CHILDREN'S READING, PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT AND AESTHETIC EXPE=RESSION OF NATIONALITY IN THEM E Conference Zone, 47-51.

